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EXPLORATIONS IN FATEHABAD DISTRICT HARYANA (TOHANA TEHSIL)

Vivek Dangi*, Arun Singh**, Anju Bala***,
Rajiv Maan*, Manish Kumar*, Vijay Kumar*,
Parveen Kumar*, Mandeep Kumar***

Introduction

The area under the present study is rich in archaeological remains and the fact it has been proved by the explorations and excavations conducted by various scholars. In this area, the river Ghaggar played an important role in attracting the early farming communities. The credit for initiating archaeological field work goes to Suraj Bhan (1972;1975). Thereafter in 1982 Chander Pal Singh and Dhoop Singh of Department of Archaeology and Museum, Haryana conducted archaeological explorations in this region and discovered a number of sites (IAR 1985-86:25-29). J.P. Joshi and Madhu Bala also reported some sites in 1980s (Joshi 1993). Krishana of the M.D. University, Rohtak conducted explorations in the Ratia tehsil in 2004 (Krishana 2008:12-32). Vivek Dangi of M.D. University, Rohtak, carried out village to village survey in Tohana tehsil of Fatehabad (Dangi 2010). Besides these explorations, excavations of a few sites such as Banawali (Bisht 1982), Kunal (Khatri and Acharya 1995:84-86), Bhirrana (Rao *et al.*, 2005:60-68) and Burj (Singh *et al.* 2010:94-101) have largely contributed in understanding the proto-historic urbanization in this region.

Topography and drainage system

The area is a part of the Ghaggar plain and its southern and western portions are marked by a sluggish transition to the Thar desert. The topography of the region owes its existence to geomorphic processes having closer affinity with the arid climate, both in the recent and past geologic periods. The dominating features of the topography are the Aeolian deposits of various shapes and thickness overlying the Pleistocene alluvium that can be observed in the western and northern side of the area. The mean altitude of the region varies between 210 m and 220 m above the mean sea level. The area can be divided in three topographic units viz. Sub-recent alluvial plain, Late Quaternary to Sub-recent sand dune area and Plain with sand dunes. The Ghaggar is an intermittent river of India which originates in the Sirmaur district of Himachal Pradesh and is perennial only in the upper reaches. During the monsoons it receives enough water from its tributaries viz. Markanda, Rakshi, Natkti etc. Sometimes it floods a large part of Punjab, Haryana and Rajasthan and enters Pakistan near Anupgarh (district Sri Ganganagar, Rajasthan) where it is known as *Hakra*, *Raini*, *Nara* and *Wahid*. *Musa Khera* (village Ratta Theh,) is a swamp in the region, which is surrounded by high

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sand-dunes towards east, west and south, and the Ghaggar passes by northern part.

Methodology

1) The present researcher conducted an extensive village-to-village survey in the region. A GPS handset (Garmin, GPSmap 60CSx) was used to record correct co-ordinates of the sites. Proper sampling of the pottery and other remains from the surface and exposed sections was done. On the basis of ecological conditions and detailed analysis of the ancient settlements, different categories of the sites like regional centers, villages, industrial centers and camp sites have been identified. The main emphasis was laid on locating sites and on observing the distribution

pattern of the cultural remains in the area. The date of the sites was decided on the basis of occurrence of diagnostic ceramic shapes of ancient cultures. The estimation about the size of the sites was made on the basis of the area, up to which cultural deposit was found.

2) Cultural material discovered from the survey and housed in different museums was analyzed and studied to address the problems.

3) The available published literature and survey reports including unpublished dissertations were examined and their data was also included in this study. Following table 1 is the list of sites either reported or newly explored.

Table 1 Showing explored sites along with geo-references and cultural sequence

	Site	District	Size in Hectare	Previous work	Cultural association
1	Akanwali 29°39'48.1"N & 75°47'06.8"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:32	EH, Hist, Med
2	Banawali 29° 59.7' 56"N & 75° 39' 28"	Fatehabad	7	EH, MH, LH (Excavated) (Bisht 1982)	EH, MH, LH
3	Bhirrana 29°33'16.8"N & 75°32' 52.8"E	Fatehabad	2	PH, EH, MH (excavated) (Rao <i>et al</i> 2005:69-75)	GH, EH, MH
4	Bhodia 29°37'32"N & 75°55'36.7"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:417	Hist
5	Bhurtoli 29°46'12.8"N & 75°44'11.8"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:417	Med
5	Bodhi 29°38'55.2"N & 75°47'41.9"E	Fatehabad	4	Dangi 2010:417	Hist, Med
7	Budhanpur 29°42'53.9"N & 75°48'33.5"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:417	Hist, Med
8	Burj 29°39'26.1"N & 75°38'30.1"E	Fatehabad	3	LH, PGW (IAR 1966- 67:11)	GH, EH, PGW, Hist
9	Chander Kalan 29°38'48.8"N & 75°49'22.5"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:36	PGW, Hist
10	Chander Khurd 29°39'05.6"N & 75°49'53"E	Fatehabad	1	Dangi 2010:36	PGW, Hist, Med
11	Chandpura 29°47'42"N & 75°43'00"E	Fatehabad	1.5	Dangi 2010:418	Hist, Med
12	Damkora 29°42'53.9"N & 75°48'33.5"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:148	Hist, Med
13	Dangra 29°41'20.8"N & 75°53'33.6"E	Fatehabad	3	Dangi 2010:418	PGW, Hist

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14	Dharsul Kalan 29°40'39.3"N & 75°44'12.1"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:418	EH, Hist, Med
15	Dher 29°42'15.8"N & 75°46'15.3"E	Fatehabad	3	Dangi 2010:36	PGW, Hist, Med
16	Ghaswa-1 29°41'06.8" N & 75°40'10.3"E	Fatehabad	1	EH, LH (Suraj Bhan 1972:36)	GH, EH
17	Ghaswa – 2 29°42'09"N & 76°46'24.7"E	Fatehabad	1.5	EH (Suraj Bhan 1972:36)	EH
18	Gullarwala 29°42'10.7"N & 76°46'25.8"E	Fatehabad	1	Dangi 2010:37	EH, MH, Hist
19	Haderpur 29°42'32.8"N and 75°47'59.7E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:38	LH, Hist, Med
20	Jakhal 29°47'19.6"N & 75°49'06.7"E	Fatehabad	3	Dangi 2010:38	EH, Hist
21	Jamalpur Shekhal-1 29°41'59.1"N & 75°50'05.4"E	Fatehabad	4	Dangi 2010:38	LH, Hist, Med
22	Jamalpur Shekhal-2 29°42'15.1N & 75°49'21.6"E	Fatehabad	3	New Site	Med
23	Kamalwala 29°36'10.8"N & 75°53'55.6"E	Fatehabad	1	Dangi 2010:38	EH, Hist
24	Kanhari-1 29°40'44.3"N & 75°56'09.2"E	Fatehabad	1	Dangi 2010:420	Hist
25	Kanhari-2 29°39'59.8"N & 76°56'19.7"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:420	EH, PGW, Hist
26	Karandi 29°42'24.07"N & 75°41'18.8"E	Fatehabad	2.65	Dangi 2010:420	Hist, Med
27	Kaul Garh 29°41'16.8"N & 75°37'14.3"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:39	EH, PGW, Hist
28	Kullan 29°40'02.8"N & 75°43'45.3"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:39	PGW, Hist, Med
29	Kunal 29°37'26"N & 75°39'50.9"E	Fatehabad	1.2	PH, EH, MH Excavated (Khatri and Acharya 1995:84-86)	GH, EH, MH, PGW
30	Lalanda 29°38'36.5"N&75°52'28.9"E	Fatehabad	5	Dangi 2010:40	Hist
31	Laluwala 29°38'07.1"N & 75°27'28.8"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:421	EH, LH
32	Loha Khera 29°40'07.9"N & 75°54'31.4"E	Fatehabad	4	Dangi 2010:41	PGW, Hist, Med
33	Malaheri 29°38'59.2"N & 75°55'42.7"E	Fatehabad	2	New Site	Hist, Med
34	Mirrana 29°42'47.7" N & 75°32'08."E	Fatehabad	1	Dangi 2010:41	PGW
35	Mundhlian 29°45'26.2"N & 75°43'21.6"E	Fatehabad	1	Dangi 2010:41	EH, Hist
36	Nangla 29°36'46.8"N & 75°53'18.9"E	Fatehabad	3	Dangi 2010:423	Med
37	Nangli-1 29°36'02.4"N & 75°54'46.9"E	Fatehabad	5	Dangi 2010:41	EH, Hist
38	Nangli-2 29°36'10.8"N 75°53'55.6"E	Fatehabad	5	Dangi 2010:423	Hist, Med

39	Ratta Theh-1 29°42'56.5"N & 75°43'10.8"E	Fatehabad	1	MH, LH (Suraj Bhan 1972:37)	EH
40	Ratta The-2 29°44'02.4"N & 75°43'08"E	Fatehabad	5	Dangi 2010:424	Hist
41	Ratta Khera 29°39'54.8"N & 75°52'26.2"E	Fatehabad	5	Dangi 2010:424	Hist
42	Sadhanwas 29°47'31.8"N & 75°46'44.3"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:424	Hist, Med
43	Samain 29°37'32"N & 75°55'36.7"E	Fatehabad	2	Dangi 2010:42	PGW
44	Sidhani 29°48'38.3"N & 75°43'17.5"E	Fatehabad	6	Dangi 2010:424	Hist, Med
45	Talwara 29°46'39.1"N & 75°48'48.3"E	Fatehabad	3	EH, PGW (Suraj Bhan 1972: 37), (Dangi 2010:42)	GH, EH, PGW, Hist
46	Zabatwala 29°3'39.2"N & 75°42'00.1"E	Fatehabad	3	Dangi 2010:425	Med

Table 1 Showing explored sites along with geo-references and cultural sequence
GH= Ghaggar Hakra, EH= Early Harappan, MH=Mature Harappan, LH=Late Harappan,
PGW=Painted Grey Ware, Hist=Historical, Med=Medieval.

Fig 1. Map showing location of the study area

Discussion

In the alluvial plain, no Neolithic site has been identified. Some scholars think that there was a hiatus between the Stone Age culture and the beginning of Pre-Harappan cultures in the region (Kumar 2009:7). Domali, district Kapurthala has yielded 14 celts of Neolithic traditions and Early Harappan pottery (Sharma & Sharma 1982). The findings of Domali are very important regarding

the chronology of the vertical development in the Punjab plains. Some C^{14} dates from Bhirrana fall in fifth millennium BCE (Rao *et al* 2005:68) but no Neolithic object so far has been reported from the site. It is quite possible that early settlers of the Ghaggar plains the Neolithic people used tools of wood and other perishable material (Dangi 2011:78).

Prior to 1970 generally Harappan and non Harappan terms were used for ceramic assemblages. When deposit or pottery was discovered underneath Harappan remains, it was regarded as the 'Pre-Harappan' because the Early Harappan phase was either uncertain or was not recognized. The term 'Pre-Harappan' has been relentlessly used for distinguishing the non-Mature Harappan material found at various sites.

F.A. Khan was the first scholar who pointed out some resemblance in the material evidence found in the Kot Dijian deposits at Kot Diji and those of the 'Mature Harappan' culture (Khan 1958). The early occupation lying below the Mature Harappan deposit at Kalibangan, Banawali, Siswal and Sothi was earlier termed as 'Pre-Harappan' and later the excavator of Kalibangan addressed it as Early Harappan. The term 'Pre-Harappan' itself is ambiguous because it creates the impression of chronological gap between the 'Pre-Harappan' period and the 'Mature Harappan'. M.R. Mughal was the first scholar who used the term 'Early Harappan' instead of 'Pre-Harappan' (Mughal 1970:6). Here the term 'Early Harappan' stands to define the culture which flourished in the study region during the first half of the 3rd millennium BCE, whereas the term 'Ghaggar-Hakra' stands for the culture which developed in the upper Ghaggar basin in the 4th millennium BCE (Dangi and Kumar 2010) before Early Harappan culture. The Ghaggar-Hakra phase of Upper Ghaggar basin is contemporary to Ravi phase at Harappan. Earlier this culture was labelled as the Hakra Culture (Khatri and Acharya 1995:84-86; Rao *et al.*, 2005:60-68). But the term Hakra or Regional Hakra is not appropriate for the upper Ghaggar basin because there are a lot of differences in the material culture recovered from the Cholistan region and Haryana (upper Ghaggar basin). The Ghaggar-Hakra repertoire at Kunal and Bhirrana occurs in a separate horizon and

indicates a very early village development in the region. In the area under the present study, there are six sites which have yielded pottery of this Ghaggar-Hakra tradition. Earlier this culture was known through the excavations only at Kunal and Bhirrana but the present study brought to light three more sites. A vase was recovered from.

Early Harappan

This cultural phase succeeds the Ghaggar-Hakra culture in the region and is represented by the characteristic Sothi-Siswal ceramics, with the influence of Kot Diji elements. On the basis of Carbon-14 dates from Kalibangan and Bhirrana we can assign this cultural phase to the early 3rd millennium BCE. The Sothi-Siswal culture is a regional variant of the Early Harappan culture in the upper and middle Ghaggar basin, although we are getting some foreign elements in the ceramics like surface treatments and decorations akin to the pottery in western Punjab. This might be due to the contacts and interactions between these regions. The excavation at Bhirrana proved that there was a continuity of the Sothi-Siswal elements (especially ceramics) in the succeeding Mature Harappan phase (Rao *et al* 2005:61). Also at Banawali, a similar scenario was noticed (Bisht 1982:116). It is the formative period of the urban Harappan phase. As many as eighteen sites of this culture have been explored in the area under the present study. All the five sites of the Ghaggar-Hakra period were occupied by the Early Harappans. The rest of the 14 sites were laid on the fresh ground. Most of these sites have multi-cultural deposits. The ceramic assemblages have affinity with the Sothi-Siswal pottery.

Mature Harappan period

The cultural phase that follows the Early Harappan period in the region represents the urban Harappan civilization. A total of 7 sites related to this phase were explored, which yielded

classical Harappan pottery and antiquities. It is quite strange that the number of sites during the urban phase decreased. It is quite possible that some of the Early Harappan villages maintained their character during the Mature Harappan phase and perhaps therefore devoid of classical Harappan elements, especially ceramics. Also that the Early Harappan ceramics survived into the Mature Harappan period and transformed into a ceramic style of the Late Harappan. The comparative quantity of classical Harappan pottery is much lesser than other local pottery. It appears that ceramic tradition of the Sothi-Siswal culture continued throughout the Mature Harappan phase. Mitathal also yielded the similar evidence as a good number of pot sherds have affinity with the regional Early Harappan culture in Period IIA (Suraj Bhan 1975:23). Suraj Bhan on the basis of the Mitathal excavations clearly mentioned that between Siswal-B (Early Harappan culture) and Late Siswal (Mature Harappan) there is no cultural break (Suraj Bhan 1975:6-7). It was noticed that the Harappan and non-Harappan types (Sothi-Siswal traditions) were found throughout the cultural phases (Uesugi 2011: 85-86). During the explorations, the scholars including the present author identified Mature Harappan sites on the basis of typical Harappan pottery (Figure 4), such as button-base goblets, perforated jars, dish-on-stands with long stems and flaring rims. In other words, there is a possibility that there were some rural Harappan settlements which did not adopt the classical Harappan elements but were contemporary with the Mature Harappan period. Manmohan Kumar (2009) also concluded in the same way.

It is likely that annual floods provided mineral rich soil for surplus production. The surplus production of the Early Harappans perhaps paved the way for urbanization. Now a day's also villagers along the river Ghaggar enjoy floods during the monsoon, which allows them to grow

paddy. After paddy crop, the soil has sufficient humidity to support winter crop (wheat, gram and mustard). The presence of rice (*oryza sativa*), jowar (*sorghum bicolor*), cotton (*gossypium arboretum/herbaceum*), barley (*hordeum vulgar* and *hordeum valgare var*), wheat (*triticum dicoccum*, *triticum sphaerococcum* and *triticum aestivum*) and horse-gram (*dilichos biflorus*) in the Early and Mature Harappan levels at Kunal (Saraswat and Pokharia 2003:121) indicates summer and winter cropping during the third millennium BCE.

Banawali is the western most Harappan settlement in the Upper Ghaggar basin whereas Kalibangan falls in the middle Ghaggar basin. Two Early Harappan sites, viz. Chautala and Rampura and two Harappan sites Bisshnain and Jandwala Bishnain have been reported. Between Kalibangan and Banawali it is quite strange that there are only a few sites. It was the only area which the Harappans of the upper Ghaggar basin and of Cholistan region established communication. In the Sirsa district of Haryana state the Ghaggar changes its course many times and causes floods. To control the floods Otu dam was constructed on it. It is quite possible that during the past huge floods in the Ghaggar eroded the sites. Besides, sites might be buried under the Aeolian deposit as there are a lot of sand dunes in this region.

During the course of the exploration the first author came across a Harappan seal (Kumar and Dangi 207: 135-136) which is in the possession of a villager of Bhirrana (Figure 5). This square steatite seal measures 2.40 x 2.40 cm and has a perforated knob at the back. The seal has a caparisoned unicorn standing facing right with his head raised. It is distinguished by a long tail touching the ground, a long horn with a number of barbs and excited ear. The eyes and mouth of the animal are quite conspicuous, and a low dewlap is marked by incised lines. There are three

signs of the Harappan script above the unicorn. The middle one indicates the right to left direction of writing as there is an overlap of triangle signs from right to left. Similarly, the slant of the last sign also points to the right to left writing manner. The boss on the back side of the seal is quite broad and not well finished.

Late Harappan Period

The fourth cultural phase in the proto-history of this region is distinguished by the Late Harappan culture or degenerate phase of urban Harappans. Eleven sites yielded the remains of this phase. The classical Harappan shapes like goblets, beakers, perforated jars, dish-on-stands with long stems and bowls with nail-headed rims were out of use. The common pottery types are dish-on-stands with ribbed junctions, dish-on-stands with broad and short stands, vases with projected undercut rims, jars with wide and narrow mouths, globular vases with flanged rims and flasks treated with fine red slip. Five Late Harappan sites were visited during the exploration. Out of these two sites were laid on fresh ground. As we move towards east of the study area, the density of the Late Harappan sites increase. Present day Jind, Kurukshetra, Kaithal, Patiala, Sangurur districts were thickly populated during that times.

PGW Period

During the proto-historic period, the last phase is characterized by the advent of the PGW people. The exploration yielded 13 PGW sites. The excavations at Bhagwanpura (Joshi 1993:27-31) and Madina (Kumar *et al.* 2009:114) threw light on the relationship between the Late Harappan and PGW people. Period IA of Bhagwanpura is represented by the Late Harappan people, while Period IB is distinguished by the continuous occupation of the Late Harappan people and the advent of PGW using people. Similar evidence was also reported from Madina. Here the excavator does not claim an overlap, but writes

that 'an important result of the excavation is the discovery of the Late Harappan traits during the PGW period. This is not the new phenomenon as the excavations at Bhagwanpura, Dadheri, Katpalon and Manda have yielded similar evidence ... Although the feasibility of this theory is not discussed here ... so far as our site is concerned, it is clear that there is a continuation of the Harappan traditions until the onset of the PGW culture towards the end of the second millennium BCE' (Kumar *et al.* 2009:114). This overlap of cultures is very significant and the coexistence of two different social groups tends to bridge the gap between the Late Harappan and PGW using peoples. The area under the present study has only one site which yielded the remains of both Late Harappan and PGW. Out of total 16 sites, 10 sites were occupied for the first time.

Conclusion

The researcher scholars have conducted extensive village-to-village survey in the region and recorded sites with the help of GPS, besides size of settlements and other vital information. This has helped us to correct some of the earlier recording of sites and their size e.g. Lakhmirwala, Gurnikalan-1 (district Mansa, Punjab) and so on. Recently some scholars surveyed various parts of Haryana addressing this problem (Dangi 2009a; Dangi 2009b; Dangi 2010; Singh, R.N. 2010:37-53, Singh, R.N *et al* 2011). Future researchers shall have data on which they can easily bank upon.

During the survey it was noticed that most of the archaeological sites are either converted into the agriculture fields or the soil is removed for making roads, canals and domestic structures. The situation is very grim because in a few years it will be very difficult for the archaeologists to spot any site for excavation. Even today it is very hard to spot an intact mound. Some excavated

sites such as Bhirrana and Burj were badly disturbed by the villagers, to make the land available for cultivation. Hence the present study has its own importance as the sites are now recorded for posterity which may not exist in future. But still some sites viz. Burj, have rich archaeological potentialities and if excavated or declared protected they can throw welcome light on the history and culture of the region. Otherwise like other sites these are doomed to vanish without any trace and the future generations shall be deprived of vast archaeological heritage. Some already excavated and protected site were destroyed by villagers (Figure 6).

References

- Bisht, R.S. 1982. Excavations at Banawali: 1974-77, in *Harappan Civilization: A Contemporary Perspective* (G.L. Possehl Eds), Oxford & IBH Publishing Co., New Delhi.
- Bisht, R.S. 1999. Dholavira and Banawali: Two Different Paradigms of the Harappan Urbis Forma, *Puratattva* 29: 14-42.
- Dangi, Vivek 2011. Explorations along the river Ghaggar and Sirhind Nala Haryana and Punjab, *Man and Environment* XXXVI (2): 66-87
- Dangi, Vivek 2010; *A Study of Proto-Historic settlements in Upper Ghaggar Basin*. Ph.D. Dissertation. Rohtak: Maharshi Dayanad University.
- Dangi, Vivek 2009a. *Archaeology of Ghaggar Basin: Settlement Archaeology of Meham Block, district Rohtak, Haryana, India, Occasional Paper 7: Linguistics, Archaeology and the Human Past*. Kyoto: Indus Project.
- Dangi, Vivek 2009b. Recent explorations in the Chautang Basin (Jind District, Haryana), in *Occasional Paper 9: Linguistics, Archaeology and the Human Past* (T.Osada and Akinori Useuagi Eds) pp 73-163. Kyoto: Indus Project.
- Dangi, Vivek, 2006, *Settlement Pattern of Meham Block District Rohtak*. M.Phil. Dissertation. Kurukshetra: Kurukshetra University.
- Gosh. A 1952. The Rajputana Desert- its Archaeological Aspect, in *Bulletin of the National Institute of Science of India*, No. 1:37-42
- Hissar district Gazetteer 1987:7
- India Archaeology: A Review 1962-63. New Delhi: Archaeological Survey of India.
- Indian Archaeology: A Review 1966-67. New Delhi: Archaeological Survey of India.
- Indian Archaeology: A Review 1985-86. New Delhi: Archaeological Survey of India.
- Joshi, Jagat Pati 1993. *MASI no. 89 Excavation at Bhagwanpura 1975-76 and other explorations & Excavations 1975-81 In Haryana, Jammu & Kashmir and Punjab*. New Delhi: Archaeological Survey of India.
- Kenoyer, J.M., 1998. *Ancient Cities of the Indus Valley Civilization*. Karachi :Oxford University Press.
- Khan, F.A 1958. *Preliminary Report on the Kot Diji Excavation 1957-58*. Karachi: Department of Archaeology.
- Khatri, J.S. and M. Acharya 1995. Kunal: A New Indus Saraswati Site, *Puratattva* 25: 84-86.
- Konasukawa, A, Hitoshi Endo, Akinori Useugi, 2011. Minor Object from the Settlement Area, in *Excavations at Farmana, District Rohtak, Haryana, India, 2006-08* (Vasant Shinde, T.Osada, Manmohan Kumar Eds.), Kyoto:Indus Project.
- Krishana 2008. *Archaeology and History of Ratia block, District Fatehabad*, M.Phil Dissertation. Rohtak: Maharshi Dayanad University.
- Kumar, Manmohan 2009. Harappan Settlements in the Ghaggar-Yamuna Divide, in *Occasional*

- Paper 7: Linguistics, Archaeology and the Human Past* (T. Osada and Akinori Uesugi Eds.) pp 1-78. Kyoto: Indus Project.
- Kumar, Manmohan and Vivek Dangi 2007. A Harappan Seal from Bhirrana, in *Numismatic Studies Vol. 8.* (Manmohan Kumar Eds) pp 135-136. New Delhi: Harman Publishing House..
- Kumar, Manmohan, V. Shinde, A. Uesugi, Vivek Dangi, Sajjan Kumar and Vijay Kumar 2009. Excavations at Madina, District Rohtak, Haryana 2007-08: A Report, in *Occasional Paper 7: Linguistic Archaeology and the Human Past* (T. Osada and Akinori Uesugi Eds.). pp 77-177. Kyoto: Indus Project.
- Mughal, M.R. 1970. *The Early Harappan Period in the Greater Indus Valley and Northern Baluchistan (c.3000-2400 B.C.)*. Ph.D Dissertation. Pennsylvania: University of Pennsylvania.
- Mughal, M.R., 1997. *Ancient Cholistan: Archaeology and Architecture*. Karachi: Ferozsons.
- Nath, A, 2001. Rakhigarhi: 1999-2000, in *Puratattva* no.31: 43-46.
- Nigam, J.S. 1979. Harappan Pottery, in *Essays in Indian Protohistory* (D.P. Agrawal and D.K. Chakrabarti Eds.). New Delhi: B.R Publishing House.
- Rao, L.S., N.B. Sahu, Prabash Sahu, Samir Diwan and U.A. Shastry 2005. New Light on the Excavation of Harappan Settlement at Bhirrana, *Puratattva* 35: 60-68.
- Rao, L.S., N.B. Sahu, Prabash Sahu, U.A. Shastry and Samir Diwan 2004. Unearthing Harappan Settlement at Bhirrana, *Puratattva* 34: 20-24.
- Rao, L.S., Nandhani. B. Sahu, U.A. Shastry Prabash Sahu and Samir Diwan 2006. Bhirrana Excavations-2005-06, *Puratattva* 36: 45-49.
- Saraswat, K.S and Anil Pokharia 2003. Palaeoethnobotanical Investigations at Early Harappan Kunal, *Pragdhara* 13:105-139.
- Sarkar, Jadunath 1978. *Ain-i-Akbari* Vol. 11. Calcutta.
- Sharma, Y.D and G.B. Sharma 1982. A New Pre-Harappan Site in Punjab with likely Neolithic Stratum, in *Indian Archaeology –New perspective* (R.K. Sharma Eds.). New Delhi: Agam Kalan Prakashan.
- Singh, R.N., C.A. Patrie, C.A.I. French, S. Neogi, A.K. Pandey, D. Parikh and V. Pawar 2010. Geoarchaeological Survey and Excavations at Burj 2010, Fatehabad, Haryana, *Puratattva* 40: 94-101.
- Singh, R.N., C.A. Petrie, V. Pawar, A.K. Pandey, S. Neogi, M. Singh, A.K. Singh, D. Parik and C. Lancelotti 2010. Changing Patterns of Settlements in the Rise and Fall of Harappan Urbanism and Beyond: a Preliminary Report on the Rakhigarhi Hinterland Survey 2009, *Man and Environment* XXXV(1):37-53).
- Suraj Bhan 1972. *Prehistoric Archaeology of the Saraswati and Drishadvati Valley(Haryana)*. Ph.D. Dissertation: Vadodara: M.S. University, Baroda.
- Suraj Bhan 1975. *Excavation at Mitathal (1968) and other Exploration in Sutlej-Yamuna Divide*. Kurukshetra: Kurukshetra University Press.
- Uesugi, Akinori 2011. Pottery from Settlement Area, in *Excavations at Farmana, District Rohtak, Haryana, India 2006-2008* (Vasant Shinde, Toshiki Osada and Manmohan Kumar Eds). Kyoto: Indus Project.
- Dangi, Vivek and Manmohan Kumar 2010, Pre-Harappans of the Ghaggar Basin, paper presented in the Bhuj Round Table International Conference on Gujrat Harappan and Chalcolithic (paper entitled "Ghaggar-Hakra Culture: Old Evidences and Fresh observations" was accepted for the publication in the preceding of the conference).